

Hedgerow planting to reach net zero targets could enhance farmland biodiversity

Summary

The UK government has agreed to a Net Zero greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions target by 2050, delivering the UK's contribution to the Paris Agreement, which aims to keep global temperature rise below 2°C.

Agriculture, currently contributing ~10% of total UK GHG emissions, has the unique ability to mitigate GHG losses and sequester carbon directly from the atmosphere. Increased planting and enhancement of semi-natural farmland hedgerows has been proposed by the National Farmers' Union and the Committee on Climate Change, aiming for ~181,000 ha in total by 2050.

Hedgerows are important structures for ecosystem services, providing natural regulation from floods, sheltering livestock and are a vital habitat for UK flora and fauna. This brief addresses the effects that hedgerow enhancement and management may have on arable farmland biodiversity as a Net Zero strategy and identifies possible contingencies to future hedgerow policy under Net Zero initiatives.

Recommendations for policy

- **Much of the research concerning the management regime of hedgerows is consistent, with positive effects on biodiversity**, particularly in invertebrate communities, lending support to hedgerow enhancement as a method of protecting biodiversity and simultaneously improve carbon storage.
- **When compared to hedgerows, other boundary features including green lanes and field margins** were shown to have greater species abundance and richness outcomes, particularly those under agri-environment schemes, making this a viable additive to hedgerow planting and enhancement.
- **There is insufficient research** into the specific impacts of hedgerow planting on farmland biodiversity, making it difficult to draw solid conclusions from the one study found that compares mature and newly planted hedgerow effects on beetles and spiders.
- **The overall policy recommendations are:** 1) further experimental research to identify hedgerow planting implications for biodiversity; and 2) agri-environment scheme regulated boundary management has important biodiversity benefits, thus should be incorporated into hedgerow planting policy.

The challenge

In order to meet the UK government 'Net Zero by 2050' goal, sector-specific strategies for GHG mitigation and carbon sequestration are needed. Agriculture contributes ~10% of total UK GHG emissions, but is also a unique opportunity for Net Zero strategies.

One scenario is to increase and enhance hedgerows, generating a total of ~181,000 ha by 2050, with the NFU estimating a carbon sequestration potential of 0.5 million tonnes carbon dioxide (Mt CO₂) equivalent per year. However, the implications of this scenario on the biodiversity that occupy farmland hedgerows that are to be enhanced through management or newly planted was uncertain.

The main objective of this policy brief was to evaluate the impacts of hedgerow enhancement on arable farmland biodiversity in the UK and identify any contingencies that may increase the effectiveness of this Net Zero strategy in a biodiversity-context.

The method

This brief was generated from a rapid review of arable farmland literature in March 2020 that analysed the impacts of hedgerow planting and enhancement (i.e. management) on biodiversity abundance and richness measures.

Search: Searches were performed in ISI Web of Science, Scopus and Google Scholar to identify relevant English language research articles from both peer-reviewed and grey literature databases.

The first sift extracted studies based on title and abstract (n = 48), duplicates (n = 29) were then removed and a second sift by full text review of these papers left 6 studies. The bibliographies of these final papers were also searched for relevant material (n = 2; total n = 8 papers).

Extraction: From the final eight papers, summary information relating to the PICOS format was extracted. In a separate table, the methods and abundance and/or richness outcomes were recorded, and a critical appraisal of the studies was made based on causation, outcome measurements and selective reporting.

Synthesis: Studies were grouped by intervention type, falling into three categories:

- i) hedgerow management,
- ii) comparisons of boundary features and
- iii) mature vs newly planted hedgerow effects.

A meta-analysis was not performed. Overall effect of the intervention was noted, with any contingencies of its' effectiveness that could be important in the policy making process.

The results

The eight primary research articles collated spanned ten years. Six papers focussed on hedgerow management effects, using conventional techniques (e.g. annual, autumn-cutting) or unmanaged hedges as a comparator.

The main findings from these papers fell under current AES guidance, e.g. biennial or triennial management, particularly in winter, was preferable for butterflies, although a similar study using moths found no significant differences in management timing or frequency. Secondly, coppicing, hedge-laying and gapping-up was shown as a positive influence on biodiversity. Lastly, a switch from conventional hedge-laying techniques to wildlife hedge-laying may be a more cost-effective method of maintaining invertebrate abundance in hedgerows whilst enhancing them.

One study analysed the impacts of hedgerows, grass banks and green lanes (double hedges) on butterfly numbers and richness. Green lanes supported more butterflies than single hedgerows, suggesting a possible contingency for policy as green lanes support a more connected habitat area.

The final paper looked into the effects of habitat age (mature vs newly planted) in hedgerows and field margins on invertebrates. There were significantly more beetles and spiders in hedgerows, although no differences in hedgerow age were found. New hedges may take ≥ 5 years to be colonised by diverse invertebrate communities and may attract pest species.

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Find out more

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